

methoxide from an automatic burette till the colour changes from yellow to yellowish green. Blank determinations are carried out using the same volumes of the solvents in the respective cases and the values of the blanks are deducted from the values of actual determinations.

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Sensitive Micro Determination of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} with Some Triphenylmethane Dyes in Presence of Micelle Forming Cationic Surfactant

CHANDRASHEKHAR VEKHANDI and KAILASH N. MUNSHI

Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur (India)

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THE addition of certain long chain quaternary salts render the highly coloured solutions of triphenylmethane dyes to almost colourless. This is expected from the interaction of these dyes with

cation active detergents on account of the relatively high charge within certain pH ranges forming micellar aggregates. The complexes formed with these modified dyes with certain metal ions show extreme rise in the sensitivity and thus yields very sensitive reagents for the micro determination of metal ions.

In our earlier communications, we have reported the use of some triphenylmethane dyes viz., methyl thymol blue (MTB)⁴, chromeazurol S (CAS)⁵, eriochrome azurol B (ECAB)⁶, and solochrome cyanine R (SCR)⁷ in presence of micelle forming cationic surfactants for the micro determination of rare-earths. This paper reports in brief a comparative data of the colour reactions produced between UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} and the above mentioned reagents including pyrocatechol violet (PCV) and Gallein (GAL) in presence of micelle forming cationic surfactant, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) to explore the possibility of use as sensitive reagents for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . Out of these CAS⁵ and SCR⁷ in presence of CTAB have earlier been suggested as sensitive reagents for UO_2^{2+} . CAS⁵ in presence of CTAB has also been reported earlier as a sensitive reagent for Th^{4+} .

Tables 1 and 2 record some useful analytical data for these complexes.

A comparison of these data reveals that ECAB appears to be quite sensitive reagent for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . PCV, GAL and SCR can also be recommended as quite sensitive. These reagents are, however, not specific for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . However, most of the cations are found not to interfere. The metal ions which interfere in all the cases are Fe^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Be^{2+} , Ag^+ , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Sm^{3+} and PO_4^{3-} . Mutual interference of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} was also noted. ECAB is comparatively exposed to lesser interference by foreign ions.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR URANYL COMPLEXES IN PRESENCE OF CTAB

	MTB	ECAB	PCV	GAL
pH of study	6.0	4.5	6.0	3.20
λ_{max} of study (nm)	620	630	660	600
Shift in λ_{max} in presence of CTAB (nm)	600 to 620	620 to 630	600 to 660	540 to 600
Composition of complexes (M:L)	1:1	1:2	1:1	1:1
Formation Constants (log K)	4.2	10.1	5.0	5.7
Effective photometric range (ppm)	1.19-3.37	0.27-0.81	0.59-1.78	2.1-4.18
Molar absorptivity	3.8×10^4	9.6×10^4	6.24×10^4	4.16×10^4
Sensitivity (Sandell) $\mu g/cm^2$	0.0049	0.0015	0.0031	0.0040

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR Th^{4+} COMPLEXES IN PRESENCE OF CTAB

	MTB	SCR	ECAB	PCV	GAL
pH of study	5.0	4.5	4.5	5.8	3.20
λ_{max} of study (nm)	600	600	600	660	590
Shift in λ_{max} in presence of CTAB (nm)	Nil	520 to 600	570 to 600	600 to 660	540 to 590
Composition of Complexes (M:L)	1:1	1:2	1:2	1:1	1:1
Formation Constants (log K)	4.2	10.1	10.1	5.0	5.6
Effective photometric range (ppm)	1.15-3.38	1.11-3.48	0.55-1.48	0.53-1.74	1.19-3.62
Molar absorptivity	3.43×10^4	7.20×10^4	8.56×10^4	5.19×10^4	4.71×10^4
Sensitivity (Sandell) $\mu g/cm^2$	0.0049	0.0019	0.0015	0.0034	0.0037

*Spectrophotometric Determination of Metal ions with Modified reagents :**General Procedure :*

Adjust the pH of the metal ion solution containing 6 to 70 μg (*see* Tables 1 and 2 for effective range) to the required pH (Tables 1 and 2). Add 2 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ modified reagent solution of the same pH (The modified reagents are prepared by adding about four fold excess of CTAB solution to reagent solutions and keeping them for atleast 15-20 minutes for complete micelle formation). Make up the volume to 25 ml with distilled water. Measure the absorbance at suitable wave length (Tables 1 and 2) against modified reagent as blank. The results obtained should be compared with a calibration curve prepared according to the same procedure.

The reproducibility of the reaction was found to be excellent with ECAB, PCV and SOR.

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**Kinetics of the Oxidation of Methyl Phenyl Sulphoxide by Chloramine-T in Acid Medium :
Effect of Low Acid Concentrations**

K. GANAPATHY* and P. JAYAGANDHI

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University,
Annamalainagar-608 101

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In a previous communication the authors¹ have reported on the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphoxide in the presence of hydrochloric acid (0.04-0.08 M) and sodium chloride (0.40 to 0.70 M) at 10°. The rate of disappearance of chloramine-T showed first order dependence on [chloramine-T], $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ and it was independent of the substrate concentration. In the present communication we have examined the kinetic behaviour of oxidation with $[H^+]$ less than 0.035 M .

Experimental

Chloramine-T used was of AnalaR grade (M & B). Methyl phenyl sulphoxide was prepared by a known method. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. The kinetics of the reaction was followed by iodometric estimation of chloramine-T in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture at various time intervals. Methyl phenyl sulphone was found to be the oxidation product of substrate¹ even under these conditions.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of the oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphoxide by chloramine-T has been studied at several initial concentrations of the reactants (Table 1). When methyl phenyl sulphoxide is in excess plots of log (titre) versus time are found to be linear. The first order constants in chloramine-T calculated at different initial concentrations of the reactants are found to be independent of the substrate concentration.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS
Temp. = 20° $[H^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $[Cl^-] = 0.42 M$ $I = 0.42$

$10^4 [\text{Chloramine-T}]$ M	$10^3 [C_6H_5SOCH_3]$ M	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ sec^{-1}
8.0	20.0	8.46
14.0	20.0	8.34
20.0	20.0	8.72
20.0	8.0	8.17
20.0	14.0	8.31

Effect of Variation of Acid Concentration :

The kinetic runs were carried out at 20° keeping the concentrations of methyl phenyl sulphoxide and chloramine-T constant at varied concentrations of hydrochloric acid (Table 2). A plot of log k against log $[H^+]$ gave a straight line with slope slightly higher than 0.5.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON $[H^+]$

Temp. = 20° $[C_6H_5SOCH_3] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
 $[\text{Chloramine-T}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Cl^-] = 0.42 M$, $I = 0.42$

$10^3 [H^+]$ M	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ sec^{-1}
1.4	7.78
2.0	8.72
2.4	10.04
3.0	11.19
3.5	12.49

Effect of Variation of Chloride Ion Concentration :

The kinetic runs were carried out at 20° with varying concentrations of chloride ions (Table 3). A plot of log k versus log $[Cl^-]$ gave a straight line with slope nearly 1.